

IMPLEMENTATION OF HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract. In this article, human resource management, personnel capacity building, personnel policy analysis, personnel selection, and factors affecting organizational culture are presented in preschool educational organizations. Also, the problems of the leader's working hours and the creation of a work plan related to his activities are highlighted as factors influencing the leadership activity.

Key words: criterion, value, personnel potential, management, factor, principle, personnel, management.

Under the leadership of President Sh. Mirziyoyev, very important tasks are being carried out in our country, that is, in the current period, comprehensive, rationally based priority tasks and directions, social and educational development plans and programs are being developed for our future in order to ensure the stable and rapid development of the republic's economy. The most important of these is "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", which was developed and implemented in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 No. PF-60 .

The leaders and specialists appointed in charge of this field have implemented the "Development Strategy" to improve the work of the state and society in Uzbekistan, ensure the rule of law and further reform the judicial system, liberalize the economy, develop the social sphere, security, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance. The fact that it is called the new "Uzbek model" of development in terms of providing, deeply thought-out, mutually beneficial and practical foreign policy increases the relevance and importance of this program.

A leader is a manager, he works with people, is responsible for their professional success and safety, organizes and coordinates their efforts to complete tasks.

The main responsibilities of the human resources manager are:

- t killing and planning of states
- Recruitment and selection of employees
- Paying and rewarding employees
- Improving the qualifications of employees and evaluating their performance .

In other words, he performs the planning, organizing, directing and controlling functions of the human resources manager .

Socio-political management is the management of relations between different groups of people (social groups, nations, communities, etc.).

the spiritual development of individual members is another main type of

management. In the age of scientific and technical development, management of the sphere of spiritual production is of great importance. This form of management includes management of educational organizations, public education bodies, science, literature, art, culture, health care.

Operational functions of human resources management are as follows:

- Recruitment
- Development
- Payment of wages
- Provide
- Lick motivation
- Integrate

Different managers, regardless of their position authority, have a common basis of management ethics according to the following principles:

- competence - having the necessary knowledge, experience and training to competently perform the necessary authority;
- humanitarianism - love for a person in a service attitude and good moral character, work aimed at revealing the qualities of the best personal work ability in people ;
- innovativeness - the desire to search for new things, to strive for them, the ability to take reasonable risks;
- pragmatics - working for results , effective use of work and time , active investment activity;
- Orthobioticity is the realization of valuing one's own life, full confidence in the future , caring for the environment .

Human resource management process :

- Attracting a quality workforce;
- Development of quality workforce;
- Support a quality workforce.

The criteria for describing the important features of education at the level of the state, society, and individual in meeting the intellectual and spiritual requirements of the individual and forming his abilities and talents were adopted, that is, the development of the intellectual and scientific potential of the state and the increase of the spiritual wealth and legal culture of the population, the worldview of the society education is directed to the development of the society and signs of social mentality, the formation of global spiritual values, if the society is in favor of the increase of educated, highly educated, spiritual, scientific potential people, the person (man) should develop the abilities gifted by nature through education, be able to show himself in study (work) , profession , specialization, satisfies the need to acquire knowledge, training, skills and experience necessary for the position he holds. After all, education is the work of becoming enlightened , one step above others . The more he has studied, the higher the level.

The creation of a personal model of the transition to a market economy has brought to light a number of problems, among which education is an organizational factor of development. Before we begin to consider the organizational factor of economic development, it is understood that we need to clarify the essence of concepts such as "organization",

"responsibility" and "authority". These concepts are definitely related to organizational factors, their organization and implementation.

An organization is an association of people who jointly implement a (human) goal or program and operate under certain laws and procedures.

Responsibility is the level and category of performance of a specific function, task and task in accordance with the laws and regulations of that country.

Authority - these functions are transferred to the state authorities , to the chief security office and to the authorities.

Based on all the concepts presented above, it can be seen that the human factor is of primary importance. Efficiency and goal achievement are determined by the responsibility for the performance of the organization's tasks and the rational use and control of powers .

From this, it is understood that the organization is the first step in achieving this goal . Therefore , the elements of the economy should be planned in such a way that the organization's goals and tasks or organizational activities are clearly defined in time and space . Otherwise, it is necessary to organize the activities of the leaders in many different ways . due to their non-receipt, there will be an out-of- production expenditure . For example, can a restaurant gain prestige if it plans and prepares a special meal but does not have tableware?

Place is allocated to functional powers . Functional authority is the authority that provides the right to make decisions on employee objects that are regularly controlled by other managers to managers , and to staff and departments .

The practical use of functional powers has always been opposed to the sound principle of the general government .

The provision of functional powers should be used carefully . In our opinion, the principle is the work and the decision Regardless of what is done, it is necessary to lead with common sense and to act with deep thought. For the correct use of functional powers, it depends on whom , who has authority , what or over whom ; why these functional powers are needed; It is necessary to clarify such questions as the principles of these powers .

Organizational problem solving depends on 2 terms: "centralization" and "decentralization " . Each of them represents this side of the coin . For example, in an organization with a fully centralized management system , the right to make a decisive decision is vested in the hands of a single official or they are allocated to a unit of his departments . In a decentralized organization, the rights are divided among several persons or departments.

Since the management of personnel training in the educational system and the coordination of the development of this process is a very important issue, the Concept of the development of the continuous education system in the market economy conditions in Uzbekistan is expressed in the "National Program of Personnel Training", in which all strategic directions of the management of the training of qualified personnel are developed.

On October 10, 2019, President Sh. Mirziyoyev signed the Decree "On measures and measures to fundamentally improve personnel policy and the system of state civil services in the Republic of Uzbekistan." In the decree, it is noted that due to the absence of an organization related to the management of state civil services, the unified personnel policy is not being implemented in state bodies and organizations, there is no effective management of personnel and human resources development, the reserve of qualified specialists based on

competition and vacancies of civil servants are not being filled on time. Also, the mechanism for selecting candidates for civil state services has not been formed, and all citizens are not provided with equal rights to work in state services. A system of guaranteed decent remuneration and social protection of servants has not been created.

People management is very important for all organizations. There is no organization without people. No organization can achieve its goals without the right people. Human resource management is an important part of management theory and practice. In large educational organizations, the general management responsibility for labor resources is assigned to qualified employees of the personnel department, which is usually part of the staff services. In order for these professionals to help achieve the organization's goals, they need to know not only their field, but also the needs of their subordinates. At the same time, if these managers do not understand the characteristics of labor resources management, its mechanisms, opportunities and shortcomings, they cannot use the services of personnel specialists effectively. Therefore, it is important for all leaders to know and understand the methods and techniques of managing people.

References:

1. Drukker, PF *Praktik management: uchebnoye posobiye* / Peter F. Drukker; per. s Eng.; pod ed. Ya.K. Marinovicha. — M.: William, 2000. — 397p.
2. Siegert, Werner. *Rukovodit bez konfliktov* / Wernher Zigert; sokra sch . per. s wet. NV Vardul, AD Bogomolova; nauchn.ed., author. Predisl. AL Jurav -Lev. — M.: Ekonomika, 1990. — 335 p.
3. *Philosophical dictionary* / VN Miroshnichenko, LV Ostapenko, EV Shahova -M., 2004.- 560 p.
4. Konarzhevsky, Yu.A. *Management and vnutrishkolnoye upravleniye* / Yu.A. Konarzhevsky. M., 2000. — 224 p.
5. Shalayev, VP *Genesis of the social system and synergetic paradigm : dis... d-ra filos . science* — N. Novgorod, 1997. -305 p.
6. Diyev, BC *Upravleniye kak obyekт filosofskogo analiza* / BC Diyev // *Tezisy Rossiyskogo filosofskogo kongressa: v 7 t. T.4.* — SPb: Izd-vo SpbGU, 1997. — P.281-28.
7. Valiyeva Feruza Rashidovna, Abdunazarova Nargiza Fathullayevna, Zakirov Alisher Akbarovich . *The importance of ensuring the mental, physical, spiritual, spiritual development of educators of pre-school educational organizations . PhD. Valieva Feruza Rashidovna // Bosma // Turkish Online Journal of Qualitative Inquiry (TAJQI) Volume 12, Issue 8. July. 2021:6919.*
8. Valiyeva Feruza Rashidovna, Sharipova Gulrukhsar Nurkabilovna. *Innovative technologies in improving the management of preschool educational organizations// Bosma// International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECSE) DOI:10.9756/INTJECSE/V14I5.94 ISSN: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 05 2022*
9. Valiyeva Feruza Rashidovna, Rakhimova Surayyo Salokhiddinovna. *Innovative approaches to preschool education management// Print// International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education (INT-JECS) ISSN: 1308-5581 Vol 14, Issue 04 2022*